

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

USE OF THE CONCEPT OF DIGITAL EDUCATION AND 3D TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF MODERN BIOLOGY LESSONS

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Abstract

The article talks about the role and concept of 21st century skills, STEAM method, 3D technologies, especially digital skills in biological education. The possibilities of forming the skills that are relevant for the modern era are indicated. What is expected from digital education as a perspective concept, possibilities of use are investigated. It was also brought to attention that biology teachers should approach the concepts of modern lesson, modern teacher, modern student from the perspective of a new conceptual framework. The article talks about the prospects of the transition to the new digital education concept in the world and in the republic, including in Nakhchivan education, the difficulties encountered, and the work to be done. In the end, the results of the research are shown with various schemes and diagrams, photos from the teaching process, and useful recommendations are given.

Keywords: educational concept, digital skills, 3D technologies, modern biology lessons.

Directions similar to the thoughts of the great thinker Murtaza Mutahhari who lived in the middle of the 20th century, "I love the teacher who teaches me to think, not ideas" as one of the basic principles of education, have gained a lot of importance in recent years (Babayeva, Z. 23) Among them, digitalization, 3D technologies, we can show the methods and principles of STEAM. The digital environment, which has already deeply penetrated the entire field of education and is developing every day, makes education dynamic, attractive and more deeply understandable. The concept of digital education includes the elimination of boundaries in the teacher-student relationship, technological literacy and an environment of mutual discovery. It is known that the field of education has not caught up with the development speed of today's technology (Babayeva, Z. 2023). Because the level of technological development in the world is increasing every minute. This creates a number of objective and subjective difficulties, along with favorable opportunities for the field of education - secondary and higher schools. On the one hand, students should know that different fields of knowledge are part of the overall digitization process. And these digital skills will significantly affect the way we live, communicate, interact and even get jobs in the future (8; 10; 14). We must also consider the issue of solving various problems to be overcome in learning and imparting knowledge. On the other hand, there should be qualified personnel who can use technologies in the delivery of scientific knowledge in the training process. Because the elements included in digital competence, as well as educational implementation and communicative competence, have different characteristics. It is necessary to add the competence of subject teachers to adapt the material they teach to new standards. Digital competence should no longer be understood only as ICT and also information literacy skills. Now we can not only talk about the ability to evaluate, store, access information. We should also develop the skills to use this information adequately and turn it into

knowledge, skills, projects, and finally products. STEAM, which affects all areas as a relevant method in the world, has created an opportunity to do interesting work in biology, where we teach 21st century skills (Babayeva, 2021: 109; Babayeva, 2023: 8). In 2006, digital competence was identified as a key skill by the European Commission and a number of proposals were made: "Digital competence refers to the critical and safe use of Information and Communication Technologies for work, leisure and communication. Based on basic ICT skills: using the computer to retrieve, evaluate, store, produce, present and exchange information and participate in communication and collaboration networks through the Internet' (Cabero, 2014: 111).

Educational institutions have always required appropriate training in various aspects of ICT, which should be on a continuous basis. What happened in the state of panic related to the pandemic, the need to organize the education in an online version, the usefulness and irreplaceability of digitization showed itself more clearly (Garcia Bellido, Gomez, Thevenet, 2019: 10).

The school community, especially the conservative section, realized that there was an urgent need to train or develop themselves in this regard. In many cases, interest and motivation in technology was presented as a tool to help solve many problems of the teaching-education process, rather than to help cooperation, social awareness, freedom, digital literacy of students. The fact that technology has not yet been sufficiently integrated into daily teaching strategies, neither in the classroom nor online, was evident in all the challenges that arose during the 2020-2021 pandemic. For this reason, it is important to seriously diagnose the deficiencies found in educational institutions and personnel potential. That is, each teacher should improve both his basic skills to increase his experience and basic scientific-digital skills to create knowledge in these new conditions (Babayeva, 2023: 51).

For the beneficial use of digitalization in education, the need for skilled, creative teacher training is not only to meet the demands of the virtual format, which is the basis for true educational innovation. It is also necessary to promote real changes in educational processes. For example, the introduction of ICT tools in the teaching of natural sciences - electronic whiteboards, Internet resources, and VR glasses, which are currently in use, has created an opportunity to create irreplaceable visualization. In order to benefit from all this, both the material and technical capabilities of educational institutions should be enriched, and the need for potential personnel should be met. For this, the digital skills of teachers should be improved in certain areas, and the educational concept and strategy should be developed and changed in this direction. For this, we currently have the opportunity to create enough visibility in our use. This has been confirmed again by the positive results achieved in the teaching of living organisms with augmented reality (VR) (9). Viewing entire 3D models of the skeletal system and connective tissues through VR glasses is an even more interesting learning method for students. Also, the animations of joints and bones in the Human Movement module, 3D technologies in teaching the functions and functions of whole body systems, microscopic anatomy, body movements and more are breaking new ground in education (10). But what we need is to find solutions to the problem of formation of professional personnel. In this case, a lot depends on the readiness of the heads of educational institutions for new challenges. Thanks to 3D technologies, we have the ability to learn and teach anatomy with more than 12,000 realistic anatomical models/structures, quality definitions according to body structure, and thousands of detailed micro-anatomical structures. In order to create a foundation for this, it is important to adapt the organization of biological education to today's requirements, to modernize the material and technical base of educational institutions, and to raise the level of teaching and learning to the level of world standards.

3D Organon has been established in more than 70 countries and is used by prestigious universities, hospitals, etc. worldwide. was accepted by 3D Organon is also the first software platform in the world to integrate an ultrasound simulator for virtual reality that does not require a mannequin or other special equipment. The latest 2022 release provides a fully immersive virtual reality training solution for medical and healthcare students with real-time volumetric scanning and detailed anatomical views. For the first time, VR controllers simulate curved, linear and cardiac probes all in one solution. In-app 3D models can add important cognitive inputs that improve in-depth understanding of key anatomical concepts and information retention. In order to take advantage of these opportunities, the heads of educational institutions should pay attention to their own strategies, while examining the reasons for a superficial approach to teacher training, modern educational concepts, and technological skills. We also observe these problems during discussions with high school and secondary school teachers. We have summarized it through years of advocacy and empirical work as a

frame of reference for diagnosing and improving teachers' digital skills. These skills are identified as competencies that 21st century teachers need to improve their educational practices and for continuous professional development.

It should be noted that "in each field there are other related competencies that focus on technical aspects and we consider these more important as we stipulate both technical and operational skills. It seems clear that in the future fields of science and professions will change, or special tools or resources that do not exist will appear" (11). For this, raising a generation with creative thinking, a different point of view, and excellent digital skills to quickly solve all the problems that will arise is one of the main tasks before us. But what is the role of digital skills in the use of materials and methods in teaching biology? For this, it is necessary to design an appropriate training program, concept and strategy that effectively meets the needs of the teaching process in order to draw attention to the training needs of teaching. Biology teachers should create opportunities to reduce the limitations of digital literacy in order to improve the quality of the teaching process and create an educational environment. For this, there is a need for teachers to increase their digital competence, to analyze the problems that may exist among the features of the developed concept, and to increase the level of development of their digital competence. The aim is to identify the terms of digital skills that are most closely related to designing the training program according to their actual needs. The results of the experiments conducted to assess the digital competence levels of teachers should be used in the field of education. With this tool, the issues of solving the problems of integrating digital tools into the teaching-learning process will be clarified. Because teachers' activities at each skill level can be evaluated (12, 13). The application and teaching of the working principle of technological tools, which are necessary to be used in the teaching of natural sciences, by professional personnel, will increase the interest in this field. Any innovation that is formally implemented is nothing but a waste of time. Over the past years, we have also accompanied a fact. Conservative or technologically illiterate teachers who do not consider it important to bring technologies into the teaching process have also accepted that they can no longer do their work without these tools after the pandemic. Therefore, they either try to develop their skills in this field, or they try to do their teaching work with help.

The result

It is already clear that our direction in teaching scientific knowledge to create the future should be the maximum use of technologies, the development of critical and logical thinking. For this, we must work to set a new goal, create new opportunities for development, and thereby shape the person of the future. In the teaching process, priority should be given to scientific-research skills - analysis, synthesis, courage of learners, free thinking. But what will integration give us - all sciences develop in an integrative way, all professions need integration, because everything in the universe is connected. Conducting experiments between schools will also provide comparative, useful results, and will

create a sense of motivation and competition in learners. The learning environment is also an important condition (creativity), and assessment is especially important because assessment allows us to determine the extent to which objectives have been achieved. In order to develop the way of thinking, children should be given tasks that are relatively difficult, thought-provoking, and require integration (15). The 21st century is based on the products of dreams (14). To prepare the young generation in the auditorium or classrooms for the new world order, it is necessary to guide them in this way: do not limit yourself when you dream. Achieving all this can sometimes seem fantastic, but in January 2023, a second-year student of ANM, UNEC in Azerbaijan prevented a cyber threat on NASA's website. He discovered an error on NASA's website, notified NASA about it, and warned them to protect themselves from a possible hacker attack. The 21st century plans to train these young people and create a standard of living on Mars and the Moon (16). In the future, the competition with artificial intelligence requires training professionals who can win.

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